

MARS STANDS IN 7TH BHAVA IN MALEFIC PLANET'S STARS AND LATE MARRIAGE

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Abstract:

Mars is called as Mangala karagan. If Mars gets positive strength in horoscope the marriage never delay. If Mars gets negative strength in horoscope the marriage always delay. Positive strength means Mars is located in Lagna/third/fifth / sixth/ ninth/tenth or eleventh bhava. Negative strength means Mars is located in second/fourth/seventh/eighth or twelfth bhava. This rule is common for male and female. rasi chart. D1 indicates the strength of Mars.

Key Words: Mars - Standing Bhavas - Second - Fourth - Seventh - Eighth - Twelfth - Late Marriage - Rasi Chart - Mars Dhosha - Example Horoscopes -Rules Exceptions - Malefic Planets - Sun - Waning Moon - Saturn.

What is Mars Dhosha?

If Mars Stands in Second, fourth, seventh, eighth or twelfth bhava from lagna or moon sign or from Venus. It is called Mars dhosha or Mangal dhosha. It gets great place in marriage matching. We should match the above horoscope with one whose Mars is located in second, fourth, seventh, eighth or twelfth bhava. Thus we match the horoscopes for marriage. Otherwise the separation will be possible.

Mars Dhosha Exceptions:

There are some exceptions have seen in the ancient books.

According to Prasanna Markam Book:

- If Mars occupies its exhalation house capricorn there is no Mars dhosha
- If Mars occupies its friendly house sagittarius and pisces there is no Mars dhosha.

There are some exceptions have seen in the ancient book, "Jathaga Saaram".

According to Jathaga Saaram Book:

Whose ascendent is Aries, Scorpio, Taurus, Libra, Gemini, Virgo Capricorn, Cancer, Leo, Sagittarius and Pisces there is no Mars dhosha. From this we know whose ascendent is Aquaris and also Mars stands in 1/2/4/7/8/12 bhavas the native has Mars dhosha.

According to Palitha Marthandam Book:

According to Palitha Marthandam, who born in movable ascendent like Aries, Cancer, Libra there is no Mars dhosha, Mars stands in any bhava.

According to Jathaga Marthandam Book:

According to Jathaga Marthandam if Mars occupies the houses of Mercury, Gemini and Virgo there is no Mars dhosha.

What will Mars do in 1/2/4/7/8/12:

Mars in Lagna:

Lagna indicates one's health. Lagna is seventh house from seventh house. It is maraga stana for spouse. It indicates the death of spouse. So, Mars in lagna bhava indicates dhosha.

Mars in 2 (Family Bhava):

Second bhava indicates pleasure in family life. Second house is eighth house from seventh house. It indicates the dangers of spouse. So, Mars in Second bhava indicates dhosha.

Mars in 4 (Property Bhava):

Fourth bhava indicates, mother, land, home, vehicle, Fourth bhava destroys 1/5/9 triangle. So, the natives health and properties are affected. So, Mars in fourth bhava indicates dhosha.

Mars in 7 (Kalasthira Bhava):

Seventh bhava indicates the relationship between the native and the spouse. It also indicates the unity of spouse. So, Mars in Seventh bhava is dhosha.

Mars in 8 (Mangalya Bhava):

Eighth bhava indicates the life span of the couple. So, Mars in eighth bhava is dhosha.

Mars in 12 (Ayana Sayana Bhava):

Twelveth bhava indicates the sexual intercourse in bed and also loss. So Mars in twelveth bhava is dhosa.

Rules for Late Marriage:

We have seen three rules with example which cause late marriage due to Mars stands in Seventh bhava.

Rule:

Mars stands in Seventh bhava in the star of Sun; the native's marriage would be late.

Example Chart 1.1:

Date of birth : 15.04.1970
 Time of birth : 9.13 pm
 Place of birth : Kumbakonam
 Birth Star : Ayilyam
 Ascendent : Scarpio
 Balance Dasa : Mercury dasa 8 yrs. 3 Months 1 day.

5	Sun Saturn Merc Venus	Mars	8
Rahu	Rasi		Moon
3			Kethu
2	ASC	Jupiter (R)	11

6	Sun	8	9
Rahu Mars Moon	Navamsa		10
4			Kethu Saturn
Jupiter (R)	2	Mercury Venus ASC	12

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	12 ⁰ 37'	Anuradha	3
Sun	1 ⁰ 48'	Aswini	1
Moon	22 ⁰ 31'	Ayilyam	3
Mars	4 ⁰ 23'	Krithigai	3
Mercury	21 ⁰ 13'	Bharani	3
Jupiter	8 ⁰ 24'	Swathi	1
Venus	21 ⁰ 37'	Bharani	3
Saturn	16 ⁰ 28'	Bharani	1
Rahu	16 ⁰ 18'	Sathayam	3
Kethu	16 ⁰ 18'	Pooram	1

In this horoscope Mars stands in seventh bhava in the star of malefic planet Sun (Krithigai) Still the man is single.

Example Chart 1.2:

Gender : Female
 Date of birth : 25.05.1981
 Time of birth : 04.27 pm
 Place of birth : Tanjore
 Birth Star : Sravanam
 Ascendent : Libra
 Balance Dasa : Moon dasa 0 yrs. 0 Months 11 days

6	Mars	Sun	Mercury
5	Rasi		Rahu
Moon Kethu			11
3	2	ASC	Jupiter (R) Saturn (R)

Saturn (R) Jupiter (R)	Sun Kethu	5	6
2	Navamsa		Venus Moon
ASC			8
Mars	11	Rahu Mercury	9

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	12 ⁰ 38'	Swathi	2
Sun	10 ⁰ 32'	Rohini	1
Moon	23 ⁰ 17'	Sravana	4
Mars	28 ⁰ 39'	Krithiga	1
Mercury	03 ⁰ 14'	Mrigasira	3
Jupiter	06 ⁰ 51'	Uthiram	4
Venus	23 ⁰ 09'	Rohini	4
Saturn	09 ⁰ 29'	Uthiram	4
Rahu	11 ⁰ 16'	Poosam	3
Kethu	11 ⁰ 16'	Sravana	1

In this horoscope Mars stands in seventh bhva in Krithigai, the star of malefic planet sun. She got married at the age of 37.

Rule 2:

Mars stands in seventh bhava in the, star of waning (Amara Paksha) moon, the natives marriage would be late.

Example Chart 2.1:

Gender : Male
 Date of birth : 15.02.1977
 Time of birth : 05.53 pm
 Place of birth : Tenkasi
 Birth Star : Uthiradam 1
 Ascendent : Cancer
 Balance Dasa : Sun dasa 4 yrs. 6 Months 16 days.

Venus	Kethu Jupiter	11	12
Sun	Rasi		Saturn (R) ASC
Mercury Mars			2
Moon	5	Rahu	3

2	Mars Mercury	Kethu	5
ASC	Navamsa		6
12			7
Moon Jupi Satur Venus	Rahu	Sun	8

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	25 ⁰ 36'	Ayilyam	3
Sun	03 ⁰ 10'	Danishta	3
Moon	29 ⁰ 54'	Uthiradam	1
Mars	11 ⁰ 06'	Sravanam	1
Mercury	12 ⁰ 54'	Sravanam	1
Jupiter	29 ⁰ 13'	Krithigai	1
Venus	18 ⁰ 00'	Revathi	1
Saturn	18 ⁰ 50'	Ayilyam	1
Rahu	03 ⁰ 56'	Chitra	4
Kethu	03 ⁰ 56'	Aswini	2

In this horoscope Mars stands in seventh bhava in Sravanam, the star of malefic planet waning moon. He got married at the age of 39.

Example Chart 2.2:

Gender : Female
 Date of birth : 10.11.1985
 Time of birth : 03.53 pm
 Place of birth : Vilupuram
 Birth Star : Chitra 1
 Ascendent : Pisces
 Balance Dasa : Moon dasa 6 yrs. 9 Months 6 days

ASC	Rahu	3	4	3	4	Sun Mars Jupi	6	
12	Rasi			5	Navamsa			7
Jupiter				6				Moon Rahu Saturn
10	Saturn Mercury	Venus Kethu Sun	Mars Moon	Venus Mercury	11	10	9	

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	24 ⁰ 11'	Revathi	3
Sun	24 ⁰ 18'	Visagam	2
Moon	23 ⁰ 46'	Chitra	1
Mars	14 ⁰ 59'	Hastham	2
Mercury	17 ⁰ 10'	Jyesta	1
Jupiter	15 ⁰ 46'	Sravanam	2
Venus	07 ⁰ 20'	Swathi	1
Saturn	05 ⁰ 33'	Anuradha	1
Rahu	14 ⁰ 53'	Bharani	1
Kethu	14 ⁰ 53'	Swathi	3

In this horoscope Mars stands in seventh bhava in Hastham, the star of malefic planet waning moon, the native got married at the age of 35.

Example Chart 2.3:

Gender : Male
 Date of birth : 28.07.1980
 Time of birth : 10.02 pm
 Place of birth : Madurai
 Birth Star : Danishta 1
 Ascendent : Pisces
 Balance Dasa : Mars dasa 6 yrs. 7 Months 9 days.

ASC	2	3	Venus Mercury	Rahu	8	Mercury	Mars	
12	Rasi			Sun Rahu	Navamsa			11
Kethu Moon				Jupiter				Moon
10	9	8	Saturn Mars	4	3	Venus Sun	Kethu Jupiter ASC	

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	09 ⁰ 44'	Uthratathi	2
Sun	12 ⁰ 08'	Poosam	3
Moon	24 ⁰ 01'	Danishta	1
Mars	16 ⁰ 45'	Hastham	3
Mercury	23 ⁰ 23'	Punarvasu	2
Jupiter	17 ⁰ 24'	Pooram	2
Venus	00 ⁰ 07'	Mirugasira	3
Saturn	00 ⁰ 08'	Uthiram	2
Rahu	27 ⁰ 12'	Ayilyam	4
Kethu	27 ⁰ 12'	Danishta	2

In this horoscope Mars stands in seventh bhava in Hastham, the star of malefic planet waning Moon. So, the native got married at the age of 40.

Rule 3:

Mars stands in seventh bhava in the star of Saturn the native's marriage would be late.

Example Chart 3.1:

Gender : Male
 Date of birth : 25.03.1981

Time of birth : 07.34 pm
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Anuradha 1
 Ascendent : Virgo
 Balance Dasa : Saturn dasa 15 yrs 10 months 9 days

Mars Sun Venus	8	9	10
Mercury	Rasi		Rahu
Kethu			12
4	Moon	2	Jupiter (R) Saturn (R) ASC

7	Jupiter (R) Saturn (R)	Kethu	10
Mercury	Navamsa		11
5			Moon
4	Rahu	Sun Mars	Venus ASC

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	28 ⁰ 26'	Chitra	2
Sun	11 ⁰ 14'	Uthratathi	2
Moon	05 ⁰ 32'	Anuradha	1
Mars	12 ⁰ 59'	Uthratathi	3
Mercury	15 ⁰ 26'	Sathayam	3
Jupiter	11 ⁰ 58'	Hastham	1
Venus	07 ⁰ 58'	Uthratathi	2
Saturn	12 ⁰ 58'	Hastha	1
Rahu	14 ⁰ 29'	Poosam	4
Kethu	14 ⁰ 29'	Sravanam	2

In this horoscope Mars stands in Uthratathi, the star of malefic planet Saturn causes late marriage. The native got married at the age of 39.

Conclusion:

In so many horoscopes Mars stands in 7th bhava in the star of malefic planets (sun/waning moon/saturn) is the barrier for marriage. The remedy for this is to worship Lord Murugar in Pazhani or Tiruchendur on Tuesday at Abijith Muhurtham (11.45 am to 12.15 pm). It removes all the evil effects of Mars and purify the horoscope. So, Mars dosha people must worship Lord Murugar in Pazhani or Tiruchendur.

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